

EFFECTS OF SiC PARTICULATES ON MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF AZ91 MAGNESIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Abstract

In this study, monolithic AZ91 alloy and AZ91 magnesium matrix composites reinforced with three different fractions (10, 15, 25wt.%) of SiC particulates (SiCp) were fabricated by rapid solidification and powder metallurgy technique followed by hot extrusion. Microstructure and mechanical properties of these alloys were examined. The addition of SiCp could weaken basal plane texture. Microstructure of AZ91 alloy showed fine grains about 1 μ m. The composites revealed that SiCp were relatively homogeneous dispersed with few agglomerations. The porosity and hardness increased as the content of SiCp increased. An increase in particulate reinforcement content was observed to decrease ultimate tensile strength but increase yield strength and elongation of the composite. The reason of degraded mechanical properties was due to increasing agglomerating regions, porosity and brittle interface debonding.

1 Introduction

The development of the lightweight structural materials is one of the biggest challenges for conserving energy in order to minimize the usage of the depleting natural resources. Magnesium alloys show great potentials as structural materials for the automobile and aerospace industries due to their low densities, high specific strength, good damping capacity, excellent machinability and eco-processing availability [1,2]. Rapidly solidified powder metallurgy (RS/PM), one of the most promising techniques for fabrication of massive bulk ultrafine-grained materials, has been successfully developed

to design high performance magnesium alloys [3,4]. Compared to monolithic magnesium alloy, different kinds of reinforcements in magnesium alloys show additional advantages such as improved fatigue, wear resistance. For instance, non-continuous reinforcements such as SiC whisker [5], B₄C [6], Cu [7] Ti-6Al-4V [8] and SiC particulate [9] have been studied by a number of researches. Generally, among available reinforcements, silicon carbide particulates (SiCp) represent most preferred one with little penalty on density at a substantially low cost [10].

However, the effects of ceramic particles on the evolution of microstructure in RS/PM magnesium matrix composite (MMC) and their influence on related mechanical properties are not well established [11]. Therefore, this study was carried out to fabricate MMC reinforced by different volume fraction of 30 μ m sized SiCp using RS/PM route, and investigate the effects of SiCp on microstructure and mechanical properties of these MMCs.

2 Experimental procedure

In present study, rapidly solidified AZ91 Mg alloy powders (particle size: 75-100 μ m) with chemical compositions given in Table 1 prepared by argon gas atomization were chosen. SiCp with the average size of 30 μ m were used as reinforcement. The elemental powders were respectively dried at 373K in a vacuum oven. Mixing of the dried powder with designed composition of 10, 15, 25 wt.% SiCp were conducted in a three-dimension blending machine. The monolithic AZ91 and SiCp/AZ91 powder were

compacted to cylindrical billets with diameter of 48mm at 493K in dry air and then extruded at 593K with an extrusion ratio of 25.

Microstructure observation and phase analyses were examined with scanning electron microscopy (SEM: JSM 7600F) equipped with energy dispersive spectrum (EDS: Oxford), X-ray diffraction (XRD: D5000X) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM: JEM 2000EX). 5ml acetic acid + 6g picric acid + 10ml H₂O +100ml ethanol was used for etching. TEM foils were prepared by a twin jet electro-polisher using mixture of 5.3g lithium chloride, 11.16g magnesium perchlorate, 500ml methanol and 100ml 2-butoxy-ethanol at 228K. Density measurements were performed in accordance with Archimedes' principle using distilled water as the immersion fluid. The samples were precisely weighed on an electronic balance having an accuracy of ±0.001g. The value of Vickers hardness is the average of at least five measurements using HX-1000. Tensile tests were performed on WDW-E100 according to ASTM E8.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 XRD analysis

Fig. 1 shows α -Mg and β -Mg₁₇Al₁₂ phases in all specimens. It is clear that the intensity of SiC peaks increase with the weight fraction goes up in reinforced samples. However, XRD analysis on all bulk samples revealed the absence of oxide composite (i.e., MgO or SiO₂), which may be attributed to the limitation of the filtered X-ray to detect phases with amount <2 vol.% fraction [12].

$I_{(0002)}$ and $I_{(10-10)}$ are selected to indicate the intensity of basal plane peak and pyramidal plane peak in order to investigate the effect of SiCp content on basal plan texture, respectively. Fig. 2 shows the relative intensity of basal plane peak ($I_{(0002)}/I_{(10-10)}$) values with different weight fractions. The $I_{(0002)}/I_{(10-10)}$ value of basal plane in composites are lower than that of monolithic AZ91 alloy, which indicates that the intensity of basal plane texture weakened upon addition of SiCp. The value of $I_{(0002)}/I_{(10-10)}$ decreases slightly as SiCp contents increases. The result in our study agrees well with Garcés et al [1,13] and K.K. Deng et al [2] 's work. The elongated agglomerating regions of SiCps are observed along the extrusion direction, which implies that the agglomerating

regions of SiCps caused by increasing contents inhibit the plastic flow of AZ91 matrix. The AZ91 alloy has to flow around the particulates and change the initial orientation, which weakens the basal plane texture.

3.2 Microstructural characterization

Fig.3 illustrates that the porosity of the composites slightly increases with the increasing of SiCp content. The reason might be as follows: the pore could nucleate at SiCp sites and the contact surface area increases as the SiCp weight fraction increases, which would resulting in higher porosity level [14]. The typical SEM micrographs of RS/PM monolithic AZ91 and SiCp/AZ91 alloys are shown in Fig. 4. The distribution of SiCp appears to be reasonably homogeneous though some clustering could be found. It is noted that Mg₁₇Al₁₂ precipitates are always located near the SiCp due to high stress field near SiCp result from thermal mismatch between Mg matrix and SiCp during extrusion. The certain orientation relationship between Mg₁₇Al₁₂ and SiC is $[111]_{\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}}//[1-101]_{\text{SiC}}$ and $(110)_{\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}}//(1120)_{\text{SiC}}$ [15]. TEM micrographs were investigated to obtain more detailed information on the microstructural features identified by SEM. As shown in Fig. 5, RS/PM AZ91 alloy mainly consists of equiaxed grains with average size of 1. Many small precipitates (β -Mg₁₇Al₁₂) distribute on the grain boundaries and inner grains. Based on Hall-petch equation, it is known that yield stress, σ , is a function of grain size, d , as

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 + Kd^{-1/2} \quad (1)$$

where σ_0 is the stress to move dislocations and, K is a constant. Therefore, fine grain size is good for improving mechanical properties. However, when high content of SiCp is used, defects become an important factor and adverse to mechanical properties [13,15].

3.3 Mechanical properties

Fig. 3 also revealed an increase in the weight percentage of SiC reinforcement lead to an increase in microhardness, which could be attributed to the presence of harder ceramic particulates in the matrix. The ultimate tensile strength (UTS), yield strength (0.2%YS) and elongation of the unreinforced alloy

and the composite counterparts are shown in Fig. 6. The mechanical properties of AZ91 alloy were higher than that of SiCp/AZ91 alloys, which may be due to ultra-fine grain size according to Hall-Petch relation as well as lower porosity and dispersion strengthening effect of β -Mg₁₇Al₁₂ precipitates. An increase in particulate reinforcement content was observed to decrease UTS but increase 0.2%YS and elongation of the composites. Further increase in SiCp content leads to reduction of UTS due to the appearance of greater agglomeration of particles and higher degree of defects and micro-porosity present in the composites. The presence of SiCp to yield stress could be summarized as follows. On the one hand, according to Orowan mechanism, residual dislocation loops formed around each particle after a dislocation bows out and bypasses it, lead to high work hardening rates and strengthen the materials. However, in the studied composites, the particles are too coarse to contribute to the Orowan mechanism. On the other hand, because of different coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatch, dislocation are created from the relaxation of the thermal expansion mismatch between the matrix and reinforcement particles and may cause an increase in the yield stress which can be expressed as:

$$\sigma^{CTE} = AMGb\rho^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$\rho^{CTE} = 16.97\Delta\alpha\Delta T f / bd(1-f) \quad (3)$$

where constant A characterizes the transparency of the dislocation forest for basal-basal dislocations in magnesium at room temperature. The dislocation density can be estimated by assuming that dislocation loops of radius $d/1.414$ are punched by spherical particles of diameter d with volume fraction f to relax the thermal mismatch due to the difference in thermal expansion coefficients $\Delta\alpha$ for a temperature excursion ΔT [13]. It is obviously that σ^{CTE} increases with the ceramic particle volume fraction and with the decrease in particle size.

Fig. 7 shows the fracture surface of all specimens. The result revealed typical brittle fracture of AZ91 alloy. In SiCp/AZ91 alloys, fracture occurred due to the debonding between the matrix and SiCp interface. SiCp are usually separated from the matrix by an interfacial film composed of MgO particles during fabrication. These films, which can be up to 500nm in thickness, will promote interparticle

fracture [15]. With the increase in content of SiCp, more brittle MgO layers are formed leading to a decrease in tensile strength. In addition, magnesium also can react with SiCp to form an interfacial reaction compound of Mg₂Si [11]. The presence of Mg₂Si layer could also weaken the interfacial bonding and cause the debonding of the particulates. There are also few particles cracking occurred. The failure mechanism appeared to be particle-matrix interfaced decohesion. The tendency for particles to fracture could be described using equation (4):

$$\sigma_{particle\,fracture} = K/(2\pi d)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where d is the flaw size, K is the fracture toughness of the reinforcing SiCp [10]. With gradual increase in strain during tensile deformation, the larger-size SiC particles fracture first, followed by fracture of the smaller-sized ones.

4 Conclusions

The conclusions for this work are drawn as follows:

- (1) The addition of SiCp could world weaken basal plane texture. The value of $I_{(0002)}/I_{(10-10)}$ decreases slightly as SiCp contents increases.
- (2) Microstructure of RS/PM AZ91 alloy consists of ultra-fine grain size of $\sim 1\mu m$ and β -Mg₁₇Al₁₂ distributed on the grain boundaries and inner grains. SiCps are relative homogeneously dispersed throughout the composite with little agglomeration.
- (3) Porosity level and microhardness increased with increasing particulate content.
- (4) An increasing particulate reinforcement content increase yield strength and elongation of the composites while decrease ultimate tensile strength. The reason of degraded mechanical properties was attribute to increasing agglomerating regions of SiCp, porosity and brittle interface debonding.

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Table1. Chemical compositions (wt.%) of AZ91 Magnesium alloy powder.

Al	Zn	Mn	Fe	Cu	Si	Ni	Mg
8.9	0.42	0.1	0.0	0.00	0.0	0.0	Balan
3	91	9	104	06	29	03	ce

Fig.1. XRD patterns of AZ91 and SiCp/AZ91 magnesium alloys.

Fig.2. $I_{(0002)}/I_{(10-10)}$ values of AZ91 and SiCp/AZ91 magnesium alloys with different wt.% of SiCp.

Fig.3. Porosity and microhardness of AZ91 and SiCp/AZ91 magnesium alloys.

Fig.4. SEM micrographs of extrude (a) AZ91 alloy, and SiCp/AZ91 alloys reinforced with (b) 10wt.%, (c) 15wt.% and (d) 25 wt.% SiCp.

Fig.5. TEM image of extruded AZ91 alloy (grain size: ~1μm).

Fig.6. Room temperature tensile properties of AZ91 and SiCp/AZ91 magnesium alloys.

Fig.7. SEM micrographs of the tensile fracture surface of (a) AZ91 alloy, and SiCp/AZ91 alloys reinforced with (b) 10wt.%, (c) 15wt.% and (d) 25 wt.% SiCp.